

DOES THE MICROBIAL ENDOPHYTIC COMMUNITY AFFECT THE SEVERITY OF OLIVE QUICK DECLINE SYNDROME? PRELIMINARY REPORT

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Endophytes are usually defined as microorganisms that exist and colonize tissues without causing any visible symptoms to the host plant, and can be isolated from surface-sterilized plant tissue or extracted from within the plant. Although the inadequate elimination of nucleic acids after disinfection of plant surfaces, makes the traditional definition of endophyte less suitable for non-cultured species, the introduction of molecular detection techniques in endophyte research greatly contributed to expand the knowledge about the hidden "endosphere" world.

Endophytes promote plant healthiness by the production and secretion of plant growth regulators, the antagonistic activity against phytopathogens, the induction of resistance mechanisms, and the supply or mobilization of nutritional elements. One of the factors that may influence the behavior towards the quick decline syndrome is the nature of the endophytic microbial community occurring in *Olea europea* plants. However, knowledge about the endophytic community of fungi and bacteria inhabiting olive tree xylem is scarce to date, and very little is known about the factors affecting the microbial distribution into the plants. Therefore, objectives of the research activities were i) to characterize the fungal and bacterial endophytic population occurring into the xylem of olive trees by an isolation-dependent approach, ii) to verify the ability of selected bacterial endophytes in colonizing the olive xylem and reduce the disease severity.

Preliminary results indicate that under field conditions, the population level of cultivable endophytic fungi and bacteria is highly variable, being mainly affected by the host genotype, host age, and wilting severity. Among the endophytic strains tested, *B. subtilis* MBBS1 artificially introduced into the xylem, was able to colonize the trees, but it induced slight disease severity reduction as compared to the untreated control.